

Stian Westerhus

Transcending the interface

Paper

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Transcending the interface

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Abstract. A musician- and composer's perspective on how working with interfaces, performative formats and exploratory instrumental practices has fuelled a deeper understanding of the process behind musical improvisation, human choice and abstract contextual musical value, this seen in the light of the present-day digital analytical tools offering new ways of definition and musical governance as the instrumental idiomatics are redefined.

Keywords: improvisation, composition, instrumental practices, idiomatics, musical governance, machine learning, AI, singularity, aesthetics.

In 2016 I started my artistic research project at NTNU called "The shape of Concerts to come". Within the project I wanted to explore the musical meaning of the instrument in my improvisational and compositional practice. Throughout my musical career as a guitarist and composer I have done hundreds of solo- and ensemble concerts and consider the concert setting, in a club, on stage, with a full-scale PA system to be an integral part of the instrument. The actual act of playing the concert has become so tightly connected to the improvisational practice I found it hard to play otherwise and I wondered if it was at all possible to detach it, change it, and to see what any practical changes done to the instrument as a whole might give musically.

The research question and strategy, I must say, was a typical one with a focus on the tangible elements of the music. Take what you know and try to change it to see what difference it makes. At this point I should note that I by no means felt that my instrument was of any hinderance to me in the act of playing these said concerts, and in fact I have felt incredibly empowered by the sheer force, and the dynamic- and expressive capability of my extended instrument, so why did I feel the urge to change it? About a year in, and I realised I didn't. In fact, it was a contradiction.

Throughout my entire career I have drawn a hard line for myself when it comes to electronics and extensions to my instrument. Yes, I have utilized electronics to extend the range and dynamic flexibility, and I have certainly used electronics to magnify extended techniques which would otherwise be impossible to use in a musical setting, but I have continually asked myself whether the electronics I used were a necessity for the way I wish to play, or if the effects, in themselves, were generatives, as in some might spell out a musical landscape I can only take part in, or even create their own music and expression where my role would be more of that to control it. If the latter was the case I would remove them in order to take back control of the instrument. I tend to think of my instrument and the act of playing it like this:

In the core, the mind - the ability to play without playing. To hear and improvise music in much the same way as I do with the instrument in a performance setting, but without the instrument. To fully engage in the music, without an output at all. Already here we might start to see where the contradictions loom.

Secondly; "acoustic instrumental proficiency". This refers to the technical ability to be so well connected to the instruments sound generators, in my case mainly strings in one way or another, or it's touch interface as we might call it in this setting, that the interface in itself is of no hindrance to the player for producing the sounds that are possible and are at the best of times directly connected to the emotional expressivity of the mind. The sound of a single pluck of a string draws from thousands of factors which is built up though thousands of hours of practice, and the proficiency not only to be able to play, but to acknowledge the capabilities of the instrument's inherent expressiveness, and to be at one with this expressive capability is all within this onions layer.

Figure 1. Instrumental layers (Stian Westerhus)

Next to the outer ring it reads "electric instrumental capability and control". This is where a physical acoustic instrument meets the electronics. In my case this as a guitar connected to the amplification without any other electronics. The sound is amplified to such a volume that the acoustic possibilities within the instrument changes. Resonances, sustain, frequencies and the interplay of feedback, not only as loud howls of uncontrolled noise, but the subtle resonating feedback in the strings, the bodily resonance of the wood, the proximity effect of certain ways of playing the strings are just some of the many aspects amplification adds to the previous layer of acoustic instrumental proficiency, and then we haven't even touched upon the technical aspects, such as gain staging, frequency linearity or volume, that play in to the abilities of maximizing the instrumental expressive potential and controllability. As with the second layer, the acknowledgement of this layer's factors should be emphasized.

The outer ring reads "assistive technology". From the subtle analogue overdrive that slightly compresses certain frequencies when pushed hard to the digital effects that can interconnect in complex ways in software. These are additional tools to the instrument and used correctly they

become integral parts of the instrument in the same way as amplification amplifies the acoustic potential. The assistive technology amplifies, or make possible if you wish, the next step of the capability. It is the electric motor in the bicycle. On its own it is useless, though interconnected to the already fully ended potential of the bicycle it not only becomes valuable in its own right, but the potential in itself is of much greater value as a whole. The bicycle is an instrument for getting you from A to B faster than walking based on your leg's muscular capability - the bicycle lets you insert your muscular potential, multiplies it by using gears and wheels, and in short gets you home in time for dinner. The electric motor takes that same potential, and extends it by helping you turn the pedals when your own potential isn't really cutting it and the going gets tough, but extending the potential also makes new things possible - like cycling up a steep hill you wouldn't even bare walking the cycle up, with your kids on the back, a rucksack full of food, whilst talking on the phone to your wife and not breaking a sweat. Great potential - great assistive technology takes that potential and multiplies it.

Now, since we are at this image of the sleep deprived father who after extending his own genetic potential in the past few years has just picked up his kids from school and kindergarten, let's back up to this idea of generatives in this outer ring of figure 1. When I say I've tried to steer away from assistive technology that dictates the music to an extent I find obtrusive, this would be calling this fathers transportation vehicle a bicycle when he was clearly driving a car. Not that I don't respect fathers who pick up their loved ones with cars, or motorcycles for that matter, but I would find it strange to see that same man in cycling wear pretending to be riding a bicycle whilst getting in to his BMW. It could be the same thing of course. He would get from A to B, but the potential that started out with his muscular strength isn't utilized in his car.

Every single slice of the onion has an interface, of course. The assistive technology needs an interface to be controlled and/or modified, the amplification - the same, the guitar is in its own right an acoustic interface for sound creation, but what about the mind - because where does this music come from? From the instrument? Is it a creation of the mind, or is it even the same as the mind? Can the mind be seen as an interface for the instrument?

I recently released a new solo album and was asked in an interview with No-Wave magazine: *"what is channelled when you improvise and from where?"*. It was a puzzling coincidence that I found myself the night before in Vega Cinema in Oslo to see the first screening of a film where I, 5 years younger, in 2015 was struggling to find answers to similar questions. In the film "Randsonen", which translates to "on the borderline" the director of the film, Tom Hovinboele, interviewed and followed six different improvisors and composers in a quest to understand what experimentation and improvisation means and the processes behind the creative output. At that time, I was starting to see the classic idea of myself as "an artist who could push hard enough to squeeze music out of the instrument with my sheer force and skill" was cracking.

The research, the instrument and most importantly the contradiction is where I would look for answers. The research reflects where I thought I could alter my music which in 2015 was starting to feel somewhat cemented and repetitive - the practical elements - the focus on altering various interfaces and acknowledging even more outer factors and interfaces like the club setting, surround sound and more - was, and still is contradictory to everything my entire musical philosophy and work method has dictated, but I hadn't seen it clearly until now.

That doesn't make it wrong necessarily but seen in that perspective there is a light that can be directed in the opposite direction. Remember, I had tried to extend my instrument in all directions to maximise the flexibility of its potentials without losing control. My view on the instrument was and still is strictly technical. It is only there as an extension and an interface to my music - and there it was! My music. My music is not the instrument. In the original research I set out to explore what would change if I changed my instrument. Of course, the instrument can be further developed to facilitate a different palate of musical expression, but it will still be my music, and if I change it so that I play my music differently - is the music, in itself, really different?

I will be the first to acknowledge the fact that yes, I do believe that my music is what it is both from playing a specific instrument and listening to related music, but that still doesn't spell out in clear text that all my music, lives within the instrument and changes from mere technical alterations to its interface and inherent powers. My musical intentions do not, but I might make changes to the instrument/interface to cater for changing musical intentions demanding greater flexibility.

If this contradiction wasn't embarrassing and challenging enough it sparked the existential question: what is my music? Not how it sounds, but more like a "what" which also needs a location - a "where is my music?". (at this point I started to wonder if this was the 40-year mid-life crisis everybody keeps talking about - I had hoped for something like a Norton Commander 750 motorcycle, or at least a fascination with BMWs.)

If I try to see beyond the creative processes, beyond the instruments inherent idiomatic, beyond the creative use of limitations, concepts, extensions and what not, beyond social or even biological factors, where does it start? How does one person end up with a completely unique musical reference?

In my mind I give meaning to musical entities and out of them music is like abstract contextual structures, and those structures - they can be interpreted as music with an inherent musical meaning. Combine this with instrumental-, theoretic- and technical ability, active referencing and an instrumental output - for me that is a general overview of my personal expression, but more importantly it describes the interface of the inner circle: the mind is an interface to the abstract measures that are uniquely us as interpreters of music and connected to the extension of the instrument - the extension being the body.

There's a saying that almost all jazz students at Trondheim Jazz Conservatoire can relate to - it's: "*you have to become your instrument.*" This is said in the context that you have to know it so well that it disappears, that it is of no hinderance to you. I can truly say that this technical ability is something I myself strive for, but this new perspective of what my music is enlarges the meaning of it. Seen as layers of interfaces the mind in its own right becomes an interface connecting the body and thus becomes part of the instrument. You have to become your mind.

If I change my mind - does it make my music different? (don't worry, it's a joke) Let us read again the description of the inner ring: In the core, the mind - the ability to play without playing. To hear and improvise music in much the same way as I do with the instrument in a performance setting, but without the instrument.

Then what is the mind playing? When I look at my six-year-old at home dancing and singing songs she can hear in her head - she's responding to the feeling of the music in much the same way as I

am when I try to practically answer the question in the interview, but when playing a concert. The only difference might be that I have 35 years more listening under my belt and have learned to develop analytical hearing and to mirror what I have heard on my instrument - recreating the ipso facto sounds of others. What I have not learned is how that feeling of music - that preference - that goose bump-moment - that, god forbid, "magic" has shaped my musical output. What happens to music in the deep states of our subconsciousness when you go through years of intensive listening to music that floods your brain with both pleasures, wonder and a feeling of belonging? You practice musical theory, instrumental technical ability, and go through the musically driven social networks, listen to music whilst going through life changing experiences. You grow up, with, together and in your music.

Remember that single note with all its thousands of factors, abstract networks of decisions formed in a single sound of an individual human's expression. People who think you can express everything through analysis and recreation have not experienced true musical meaning. Or the acknowledgement of its existence.

If seen in the context of layering interfaces - the acknowledgement of the proficiency the human mind has in acting as a managing interface of its own abstract network of musical entities is of the greatest importance, and now maybe more important than ever.

In my own practice the acknowledgement has been a pulveriser of the ego. Before I would brace myself before entering the stage to play a solo concert. It felt like a combination of preaching a strange holy gospel as much as going in to a boxing ring, ready to find this mythological focus, fight the instrument and in many ways fight myself. I had to convince myself that I, myself, had the answer. That I could dictate my music and persuade every one of its value.

With an understanding of what my music is I now have no choice but to trust it and let it be. I'm 40 years of age. I have, like most people, a ridiculous amount of musical meaning internalized, I just need to concentrate on managing it - both by acknowledging its existence and also through attaching the interface of the mind, linking the mind to the body to the instrument - in the most direct and unfiltered way - without trying to shape it or change it. There is no NO, there is no WANT. You are what you are, the rest is technical machinery, your physical body is just an extension of it as much as the assistive technology is - and your ability to make your music transcend the interface lies with the technical control of both the mind, the body and the instrument. You can't escape yourself.

Also, by doing so there is almost no need for "me" - as in the me earlier described - on stage - the ego. The decisions are in many ways already taken in that they are decisions regarding the previous musical input rather than the current output. The building of musical entities and its inherent structural potential is already there. "I" am on stage now. It's too late to be somebody else. By managing these musical entities and their inherent possible meaning through contextual relationship with other musical entities endless musical meaning is made.

So apart from being a fundamental in my own creative process, a tool to lift the focus away from the instrument and the performer as an instrumentalist - why is this more important than ever? Well, the keyword is definition - and the price of it.

With what you are about to read I should make it clear that I am in no way objecting to research on machines that take so called creative choices, but in this perspective of myself as a performer of my own musical entities - I am questioning if I can bring myself to give music that comes from generative machinery any value. I previously described the processes of removing generative parts of the instrument in order to keep a streamlined control, but as generative machinery's complexity through revolutionary processing powers is surging it is interesting to investigate what this does to the hierarchy of interfaces earlier discussed.

In a machine's abstract neural network - with an aim to take musical decisions; can the analytical powers compensate for not having a sense of itself as a being whilst learning? If we abstain from acknowledging the subjectiveness of expressivity in music - then yes, the complexity can surely act on many of the same levels but take a musical project where you have what is often described as interaction between a human and a machine. Let's say that the machine mirrors the human and both listens to the human and reacts with own sound through its generative output. What is it listening to? Does it acknowledge the expressions and emotional content, the context, its own role in the interplay? On the surface - this seems possible. If you would program it to find references in its own networks to portray a sense of emotional content to the listener, build contextuality within the music and reference human-like expressive structures, then yes, possibly you could create a sense of human-like interaction, but it would not be able to experience these feelings in itself. It has no emotions, it has no real fear, it has no empathy. What it has learned is a way of defining human output. There is of course an enormous complexity to be had within analysis and definition, but as an interface - as it might well be seen in the interplay within the fictional example, If I can play the role of the human; I would need to acknowledge the fact that I was playing with a dead being. If I played with another human I would on many levels experience empathy for their ideas and output and have respect for the fragile situation of creating music together, as I would expect the same attitude to a certain extent from my fellow musician, but with the said machine - what we would share would be the lack of empathy for each other's output.

Maybe more importantly it would bring to mind the question of what my musical meaning was worth when it would be analysed and used to create music with caricatured meaning - to put it bluntly. What would the human complexity be reduced to? The emotional content of my life flowing through the streams of music - only to be used as variables to create complexity in an output. Zoom out wide enough and it looks like there is a coherent image, zoom in and the picture is just a thousand of pieces of puzzle, all from different puzzles, in an unintelligible and thus uninteresting context.

The way I define the governance of my improvisatory musical practice, the act of creating music, define the instrument and outline a clearer map of the process - the clearer I can see which interface, tool or layer does- and affect what. The change of thought and the clearer definition of subjective musical ethics, has opened up a space that for me seems to lie between what we know, such as musical theory, technique, technicalities etc. and aesthetics. It is shining a light on how subjective musical meaning is built within a performer and the acknowledgement of its existence. As a performer the acknowledgment of musical meaning will change the Shape of Concerts to come, and hopefully keep changing my music, forever.

Stian Westerhus (Photo by Voldseth)